

Diffusion of Cations through Clay Membranes and its Energy of Activation

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Diffusion of cations eg K^+ , Na^+ , Cs^+ , Ca^+ , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , through clay membranes were studied using analytical and tracer techniques. No diffusion of chloride ion through these membranes was found. The diffusion coefficient of the ions so calculated in these systems were less than those in pure water and the order of diffusion coefficients was the same as that of the hydrated radii, of the ions. The activation energies of diffusion of various cations studied were in the same order as those of ion conductance in electrolyte solutions.

The usefulness of clay membranes as electrode for the cation activity measurements in aqueous, nonaqueous solutions has been established (Marshall¹, Bose²; Adhikari³). But a mechanism of current conduction through clay membranes has not been properly stated. Since the attempt to set up an osmotic cell with the clay as membrane failed (cf. Marshall, loc. cit), it was concluded that no liquid junction exists inside the clay membranes, which were therefore considered non-porous in a gross sense. Very recently Lai and Mortland⁴ applied the special integral form of Fick's law to study the self-diffusion of Na, Cs and Ca ions in Wyoming bentonite plugs by means of radioactive tracer technique. They showed that Na ion in clay plugs diffuses more readily than in clay films dried at 105° (D at 25° = 5.0×10^{-6} cm²/sec in clay plug and 7.4×10^{-9} cm²/sec in clay film).

A knowledge of ion diffusion in clay films dried at higher temperatures (400-600°) will be useful for interpreting and understanding the rate, behaviour and nature of ion movement in clay membrane electrodes. Since the inter-diffusion process is a complicated one, the simplest kind of diffusion study would be self diffusion in which the difference between two inter-diffusing substances vanishes. It is expected, therefore, that such a study will give a clue to the mechanism of ion transport in clay membranes and hence of current conduction when they are used as electrodes. The factors that are likely to influence self-diffusion of ions in clay films are the mineralogical composition of clays, previous ion saturation in them, water in proximity to the clay surface as well as free water, ion hydration and temperature.

Usually most diffusion studies are conducted at high concentration ranges, but as the clay membrane electrodes are valid in dilute solutions, measurements have been limited to not-too-high concentrations of electrolytes. From knowledge of the temperature dependence of diffusion coefficient it has been possible to make an estimate of the energy of activation of the process.

1. C. E. Marshall, "Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals," Acad. Press, (1949)
2. S. K. Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, **3**, 109.
3. M. Adhikari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961 **38**, 817; 1963, **40**, 373.
4. T. M. Lai and M. M. Mortland, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1961, **25**, 353; "Conf. Clays and Clays Minerals", Pergamon Press, 1962, **9**, 229.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method of preparation of clay membranes used in this investigation is the same as reported previously.³ In order to study the diffusion of electrolytes through the membrane by the analytical method, 1cc. of solution of known concentration of the electrolyte concerned, viz., KCl, NaCl, CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ is kept inside the tube closed on one side with the membrane and then placed in 10cc. water in a small beaker. The arrangement is then placed at a desired temperature in an atmosphere saturated with water vapour. After an appropriate interval the concentration of the ions in the outside solution was determined analytically, K⁺ and Na⁺ with the help of the 'EEL' Flame Photometer, and Mg²⁺ or Ca²⁺ by titration with versene. The area of the membrane was measured by a planimeter (A cm²). If 'm' be the total number of moles present in the outside solution in 't' secs, the amount in mols diffusing out per cm² per sec is evaluated as m/tA. From a knowledge of average thickness of the membrane (d cm) and concentration gradient ('c' mols/cm³), as calculated from the difference in solution concentrations between the two sides of the membrane, Fick's diffusion coefficient in cm²/sec. is calculated from the relation, ml/A d/c. The effect of change in concentration on the two sides of the membrane as a result of diffusion of solvent was also considered and necessary correction was made accordingly. The results so calculated are given in Tables I-VI.

In order to study diffusion of electrolytes using tracer elements, radioactive Na (At. wt. 22, t_{1/2}=2.6 yrs, β⁺ and γ emitter), Cs (At. wt. 137, t_{1/2}=33 years, β⁻ emitter), Sr (At. wt. 85 and 89 mixture, t_{1/2}=65 days and 53 days, β⁺ emitter) and Ba (At. wt. 133, t_{1/2}=10.0 years, γ emitter) in the form of chlorides were used in their respective non-radioactive chloride solutions. A known volume of the electrolyte solutions thus labelled was used inside the tube holding the membrane and the whole thing placed in a known volume of water at constant temperature. Radioactivity of the original as well as the two solutions on the two sides of membrane was measured after the lapse of a suitable time in a Scalar 1700 using G M counting tube⁵ (made in England by Isotope Development Ltd). From the mean ratio of the distribution of the radioactive component on the two sides, the concentration of cation present in the outside solution as a result of diffusion was found out. From these data Fick's coefficient could be evaluated. The results are given in Table VII.

For anion diffusion a similar procedure was employed. Chloride was determined by conductometric titration with AgNO₃ and sulphate as BaSO₄. For tracer technique radioactive chloride (At. wt. 36, t_{1/2}=4.4 × 10⁵ yrs, β emitter) in the form of NaCl was used with NaCl solution.

TABLE I

Self diffusion coefficients of K⁺ in different clay membranes as a function of various external concentrations of KCl at 30°

Membranes	Diffusion coefficient (cm ² sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁸ at molality of KCl				
	3.2 × 10 ⁻⁴ m	9.9 × 10 ⁻³ m	3.2 × 10 ⁻² m	1.06 × 10 ⁻¹ m	1.24 m
Aquagel Ca-form	3.7	3.68	3.71	3.8	3.8
Padegaon Na-form	5.62	5.6	5.65	5.65	5.61
Padegaon Ca-form	4.47	4.5	4.5	4.52	4.47
Contai, oxide-free, (< 0, 5μ size, Ca-form)	8.91	8.87	8.91	8.88	8.91
Contai original, Ca-form	9.1	9.0	9.2	9.2	9.0
Chinsura oxide-free, < 0, 5μ size, Ca-form	5.88	5.82	5.85	5.87	5.87

5. G. B. Cook and G. E. Duncan, 'Modern Radiochemical Practice', Oxford University Press, (1952)

TABLE II

Diffusion coefficients of K^+ , Cl^- , $SO_4^{=}$ in different clay membranes at 30°

Membranes	D(Cm ² sec ⁻¹)×10 ⁸ K	D (Cm ² Sec ⁻¹) Cl*-Cl ⁻	D(Cm ² sec ⁻¹ SO ₄ ⁼
Aquagel Ca-form	3.71	No diffusion	No diffusion
Padegaon Na- form	5.65		
Padegaon Ca-form	4.5		

*Radioactive chloride ion.

TABLE III

Self-diffusion coefficients of K^+ in various clay membranes at different temperatures

Membranes	Diffusion coefficients (Cm ² Sec ⁻¹)×10 ⁸ at			E(Range) cals/mole
	5°	30°	35°	
Aquagel	1.82	3.7	4.1	4800-5050
Padegaon Na-form	2.51	5.62	7.1	5260-5380
Padegaon Ca-form	2.2	4.47	5.6	4970-5230
Contai oxide-free < 0.5μsize, Ca-form	4.68	8.91	11.7	4470-4820
Contai original, Ca-form	4.6	9.10	9.9	4250-4700
Chinsura oxide-free <0.5 size, Ca-form	2.7	5.88	7.5	4810-5020

TABLE IV

Self-diffusion coefficients of Na^+ in various clay membranes at different temperatures

Membranes	Diff. coeff. (Cm ² . Sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁸ at			E (Range) cal/mole
	5°	30°	35°	
Aquagel	1.4	3.2	3.88	5920-6035
Padegaon Na-form	2.0	4.85	5.6	5920-6130
Padegaon Ca-form	1.4	3.55	4.14	6020-6130
Contai oxide-free, < 0.5μsize, Ca-form	2.24	5.02	6.45	6035-6350
Contai original, Ca-form	2.80	5.0	5.62	6120-6350
Chinsura oxide-free, <0.5μsize, Ca-form	1.78	4.47	5.25	6230-6350

TABLE V

Self-diffusion coefficients of Ca^{2+} in various clay membranes at different temperatures

	Diff coeff. (Cm ² . Sec ⁻¹)×10 ⁹			E (Range) cal/mole
	5°	25°	35°	
Aquagel	2.0	7.2	11.5	9665-9950
Padegaon Na-form	3.0	10.0	17.8	9490-9740
Padegaon Ca-form	2.34	7.9	14.1	9660-9720
Contai, oxide-free <0.5μ size, Ca-form	4.04	13.2	23.8	9620-9980
Contai original, Ca-form	2.68	8.57	14.6	9620-9820
Chinsura oxide free, <0.5μsize, Ca-form	2.54	9.38	19.2	10200-10730
Vermiculite	2.41	3.30		4345

TABLE VI

Self-diffusion coefficients of Mg²⁺ in various clay membranes at different temperatures

Membranes	5°	Diff. coeff. (Cm ² Sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁹ at		E (Range) cals/mole
		25°	35°	
Padegaon Na-form	2.38	8.31	13.8	10200-10450
Padegaon Ca-form	1.99	6.91	11.5	9810-10120
Contai oxide-free, <0.1 μ size, Ca-form	3.45	11.5	21.0	9940-10120
Contai original, Ca-form	2.23	7.76	13.8	10120-10570
Chinsura oxide free, <0.5 μ size, Ca-form	2.0	8.51	16.2	11230-12420
Vermiculite	1.2	1.5		3840

TABLE VII

*Self-diffusion coefficients of Cs⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺ in various clay membranes at temperatures using Cs*Cl, Sr*Cl₂, Ba*Cl₂*

Membranes	Diff coeff. (Cm ² Sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁸ at		E. cal/mole
	25°	35°	
Padegaon Ca form Cs ⁺ *	4.47	5.85	4750
Aquagel	4.57	6.17	5160
Vermiculite	nil	nil	nil
Padegaon Ca-form Sr ²⁺ *	1.1	1.82	8320
Aquagel	1.0	1.64	7925
Vermiculite	0.36	0.45	3880
Padegaon Ca-form Ba ²⁺ *	10.0	1.64	8710
Aquagel	0.86	1.41	8710

*Radioactive cation.

TABLE VIII

*Diffusion coefficients of Na⁺ in various clay membranes at different temperatures using Na*Cl*

Membranes	Diffusion coeff (Cm ² Sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁸		E. cal/mole
	25°	35°	
Padegaon Ca-form	1.31	1.88	6220
Aquagel	1.26	1.84	6340
Vermiculite	0.42	—	

DISCUSSION

1. *The effect of concentration on diffusion coefficient and possible diffusion path.* Measurements with KCl show (Table I) that the diffusion coefficient of K⁺ is quite independent of concentration as required by Fick's law. The value of the diffusion coefficient is however less than that in water, in which it is of the order of 10⁻⁵ cm²/sec at 25°.

6. B. E. Conway, "Electrochemical Data", Elsevier Publishing (1952),

There may be two possibilities for the diffusion path; a leakage exists between clay lamellae or the cation moves through the exchange sites from one to another. Since concentration of the electrolyte has got no effect on the diffusion coefficient, the former possibility is remote. The second mechanism is supported by the fact that the external solution showed no observable diffusion of the anionic species (cf. Table II). The absence of leakage through *piccin* seal was, of course, assured by employing thin tin foil and mica sheet in place of clay membranes. It is therefore suggested that cation movement in clay membrane is along the surface. A similar picture has also been presented by Lai and Mortland (*loc. cit.*) for cation diffusion in bentonite gels. In the case of cation exchange resin it was pointed out by Schlögl and Stein⁷ that the cation moves from one fixed ionic group to another along the polymer chain while the anion pursues a straight path down the middle of the 'channel'.

Effect of nature of cation and the mineralogical composition of clays on diffusion coefficient: The self-diffusion coefficient rates for the alkali cations (cf. Tables III to VIII) are of the order, $\text{Cs}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$; and for the alkaline earth cations, $\text{Sr}^{2+} \approx \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$.

This order of diffusion rate which is highest for Cs^+ and lowest for Mg^{2+} suggests that the diffusing species is the hydrated ion as in ordinary aqueous solution. The hydrated radii of these ions are: $\text{Cs}^+ = 2.5$, $\text{K}^+ = 3.0$, $\text{Na}^+ = 4.0$, $\text{Sr}^{2+} = 5.0$, $\text{Ba}^{2+} = 5.0$, $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 6$, $\text{Mg}^{2+} = 8.0 \text{ \AA}$ (cf. Kielland's values quoted by Kolthoff, Elving and Sandell⁸). A similar order of diffusion coefficients for these ions was obtained by Boyd and Soldano⁹ with cation exchange resins. With the latter the exchange and diffusion of ions may take place in the hydrated form, but according to Lai and Mortland (*loc. cit.*) in clay gel the cations diffuse in the dehydrated form. The apparent discrepancy in the present observations with that of Lai and Mortland may be due to the fact that in their work, Lai and Mortland have placed the diffusing ion on the gel surface, whereas in the present case the ions are present in solution. So from solution to membrane surface there will be diffusion for exchange, and after being fixed on the membrane surface there will be a diffusion from one side of the membrane to the other. Hence, even if Lai and Mortland's observation be taken into account, the diffusion process from solution to membrane surface may be a controlling factor, as in exchange process (Boyd, Adamson, Myers¹⁰; Bauman and Eichorn¹¹; Kressman and Kitchener¹²; Hale and Reichenberg¹³; Grossman and Adamson¹⁴). The order of diffusion of ions studied may thus be explained on the basis of their hydrated radii.

One important influence of clay structure in the diffusion process may be noticed from these data. The diffusion coefficient of all the ions studied is slightly less in the case of membranes prepared from Aquagel, the montmorillonitic clays isolated from Aquagel, Padegaon and Chinsura soils than those from the illitic clays of soil. With vermiculite (Table VII) diffusion of Cs^+ is practically nil and Na^+ and Sr^{2+} diffusion coefficients are

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14. J. J. Grossman and A. W. Adamson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 97.

also much less in comparison to the other clays. Here the diffusion coefficients seem to follow the order of the sizes of the dehydrated ions. Vermiculite clays, it may be noted, are not suitable as membrane electrodes even though their base exchange capacities are very high (Adhikari³).

Activation energy of diffusion: The diffusion coefficient is a function of temperature according to the relation $D = Ae^{-E/RT}$, where E activation energy, A constant, T absolute temperature, and R gas constant. E can be obtained from the slope of a plot of $\log D$ against $1/T$ which should be linear. The values so calculated are given in the tables in cal/mole. The activation energy is found to be greatest with Mg^{2+} and least with K^+ and Ca^+ which is the reverse sequence of the diffusion rates. The ionic mobilities in aqueous media also show a similar order of variation^{15,16}. This similarity suggests that the diffusing species, the cations in particular is in the hydrated form in the membrane^{4,16,17,18}

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The mechanism of current conduction through clay membranes used as electrodes has been but poorly understood. The nonporous nature of the membranes, becomes usually claimed questionable in the light of Lai and Mortland's experiments on self diffusion of Na^+ , Ca^+ , and Cs^+ ions in Wyoming bentonite plugs. Diffusion of cations such as K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , Cs^+ , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , has also been observed in the present study, using analytical tracer Techniques. No diffusion of Cl^- ion was observed.

The diffusion coefficients so calculated in the clay membranes are less than those in pure water. Two diffusion paths suggest themselves: (i) through clay lamellae and (ii) along surface through exchange sites. Since the diffusion coefficient is found to be independent of the concentration gradient, the first possibility seems to be remote. The second mechanism is supported by the fact that Cl^- ion i.e. anion diffusion is absent. The order of diffusion coefficients is the same as that of the hydrated radii of the ions.

The activation energies of diffusion of various cations calculated from temperature coefficient of diffusion rate are in the same order as those of ion conductance in electrolyte solutions, suggesting once again that the diffusing ions through clay membranes are probably hydrated.

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